

D ADDITIONAL DETAILS

D.1 Dataset details for Example 1

	Functions weights				A			
	Python	R	PHP	JS	Python	R	PHP	JS
t_1	0.83	0.03	0.1	0.03	0	0.67	0.67	0.67
t_2	0.33	0.11	0.22	0.33	1	0.33	0	0
t_3	0.84	0.02	0.06	0.08	0.67	0.67	0.33	0.33
t_4	0.09	0.09	0.64	0.18	0.67	0.67	0.67	0
t_5	0.29	0.14	0.14	0.43	0.67	0	0	0
t_6	0	0	0	0.99	0.67	0	0.67	0
t_7	0	0.97	0.01	0.02	0.67	0	0.67	0.67
t_8	0.68	0.05	0.05	0.23	0.33	0	0.67	0.67
t_9	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.50	0.67	0	0	0.67
t_{10}	0.12	0.04	0.12	0.71	0.67	0	0	0.33
t_{11}	0	0.23	0.18	0.59	0	1	1	1
t_{12}	0	0	1	0.00	0	0.67	1	1
t_{13}	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.10	1	0.33	0	1
t_{14}	0.29	0.14	0.43	0.14	0	1	0.33	1
t_{15}	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.89	0	1	0.67	0
t_{16}	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.10	0	0	0	0
t_{17}	0	0	0.98	0.01	0	0	0	1
t_{18}	0	0	1	0.00	0.33	1	0.67	1
t_{19}	0.11	0.44	0.33	0.11	1	0.67	0	0.67
t_{20}	0.11	0.11	0.67	0.11	0.67	0.67	0	1

Table 8: Sample dataset $\mathbb{D}$ used in Example 1 with attributes Python, R, PHP and JS. The function weights for the 20 entities are also present as columns within the table.

In this section, we provide details for the dataset in Example 1. The Example 1 dataset consists of 20 entities with 4 attributes, *Python*, *R*, *PHP* and *JS*. These 20 entities are a part of the Candidates real world dataset discussed in Section 4.1 of the paper.

The Candidates entities are $t_1 \cdots t_{10}$ and the HRs are $t_{11} \cdots t_{20}$. As any HR entity would like to find candidates whose skills are similar to that of the *job requirement*, a weighted k-nearest neighbour function with ℓ_1 distance is used. The distance function can be mathematically written as,

$$f_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^4 w_j |t_i[j] - t[j]|$$

The equation above obtains the *distance* between the requirement and hence smaller distance is preferred.

Note that we have normalized each attribute between the values $[0, 1]$. The normalization for an attribute A_j is performed for any entity t_i using,

$$t_i[j] = \frac{t_i[j] - \min(A_j)}{\max(A_j)}$$

where *min* and *max* find the minimum and maximum values for attribute A_j in the dataset $\mathbb{D}$.